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Parental Style in Influencing Student's Aggression and Self-Esteem

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Abstract :- Finding out how different parenting styles affect students' levels of aggression and self-esteem was the lashing force behind this study. 100 students participated as per the randomly from Khordha, Odisha region. Students' gender was the sole criterion for evaluation. The wholesale of the study's participants were students, in the age range of fifteen to seventeen. The calculated results presented a positive and strong correlation between aggressive parenting styles and aggressive behaviour, indicating that more authoritarian parenting styles may be associated with more aggressive behaviour. Having said that, there is no strong association among controlling styles of parenting and low self-esteem. Furthermore, a strong evidence linking in parenting styles of authoritarian to aggressive behaviour, which suggests that more authoritarian parenting methods may be associated with more aggressive children. These results show complicated relationship among parenting styles, aggressiveness, and self-esteem and that other factors might influence these results.

Keywords :- Gender, Parenting Styles, Aggressive Behaviour, Self-Esteem, students.

1.Introduction :-

1.1 Aggression :- "Aggression" means assault in Latin, where the English word "aggression" comes from. Its first use was in 1611 to characterise an assault that did not have any provocation (Punya & Hasan, 2024). Every culture has its share of aggressive people. There is violence in the world; even in the most beautiful scenery, behind the leaves and in the trees, you can see insects eating each other (Mayungbo, O. A., 2016). Psychologists from all over the globe study aggressiveness and find ways to reduce it. There is a difference between anger and aggression (Sanni et al., 2024). A strong emotional reaction to wrongdoing, anger

can take the form of wrath, fury, or even hatred.

1.2 Patterns of Aggressive Behaviour Across Genders and Stages of Development :-

From birth into old age, hostile behaviours are seen in most societies. From the fourth to the seventh month of life, aggressive expressions on the face become apparent (Chen, X., Tao, Y. J., 2016). According to research that tracks aggressiveness over time, the peak period for physical violence is between the ages of one and three and When interacting with other children, 25% of toddlers engage in aggressive behaviour, such as pushing or punching, in contrast to adults (Segun et al., 2024).

1.3 Aggression That Persists Until Adulthood :-

When children exhibit aggressive behaviour, it is easy to notice, particularly between the end of preschool and the beginning of primary school (Teuber, Z., Tang, X., Sielemann, L., Otterpohl, N., & Wild, E., 2022). Personal aggression is a predictor of violent behaviour in old age. Adult aggression is a common outcome of aggressive behaviour in children (Segun et al., 2024).

Arguments that result in violent symptoms

Aggression in its many manifestations

Unpleasant occurrences or aversive incidents are factors.

1.4 Self Esteem :- The key to a happy and fulfilled existence is a healthy dose of self-esteem. The Latin word aestimare, meaning to evaluate or appraise, is the first evidence that the English word esteem has its roots in Latin. Whether we are positive or negative about ourselves determines our self-esteem (Punya & Hasan, 2024).

What plays a role in the maturation of self-confidence?

1.5 Parenting Style :- Raising children who are content, socialised, competent, productive, caring, and contributing members of society who can build and maintain healthy relationships is the goal of parenting, often known as socialisation (Segun et al., 2024). Adequate parenting is also critical for adolescent growth. Raising, training, or educating a child is what it means to be a parent. A family's approach to raising children is known as their parenting style (Mayungbo, O. A., 2016).

1.6 Parenting Styles and Aggression :- To flourish, adolescents need their parents' affection, warmth, sympathy, and attention also The impact of parents on their adolescents' adjustment is substantial (Zhou, J., Li, X., Tian, L., & Huebner, E. S., 2020). Adolescents are more likely to flourish when they have positive relationships with their parents. Children from loving homes tend to be teenagers who are mature, kind,

hopeful, and sociable. Raised with love and care, children bring joy to their families (Punya & Hasan, 2024).

1. **Review of Related Literature :-** Researchers found no statistically positive and significant variance presented in the aggression levels in students. Finally, the results showed a small but positive association between students' aggressive behaviour and the use of various authoritative parenting approaches. No matter the gender of the wards, the study found that parents' caring and guiding parenting approaches fall short when it comes to their violent attitude at school (Sanni et al., 2024).
2. A study found that parental authority was perceived similarly by mothers and fathers. A child's sense of self-worth was more positively and showed significantly correlated with the amount of power they felt they had from their parents. Higher levels of parental authority seem to be associated with more positive views of one's self-worth (Punya & Hasan, 2024).
3. Researchers found just a small correlation between parenting methods and had little effect on the self-esteem of high school and university students. The data show a substantial association between authoritative parenting and self-esteem, suggesting a favourable relationship. Authoritarian parenting, on the other hand, is associated with lower levels of self-esteem, which may have negative consequences for the development of self-esteem in this population (Khan, 2024).
4. Research has shown that children whose parents exhibit negative parenting styles are at a higher risk of developing a low self-esteem, an anxiety, a depression, and other mental health issues. The self-esteem, confidence, and sense of competence may all be in disarray. Another way in which unhealthy parenting practices impact the maturation of the parent-child bond is by creating a chasm in the relationship between parents and teenagers. Negative parenting techniques can damage a child's self-esteem, which can affect their relationships and daily functioning even as an adult (Huang et al., 2024).
5. A study found that at the University of Lagos, students' self-esteem is positively and significantly affected by their parents' parenting style, positively and significantly by their personality type, and by the existence of major gender disparities in this regard. On top of that, students' self-esteem is positively and significantly affected by their parenting style and personality type, positively but not significantly by their gender, and positively and significantly by their personality type and gender within the University of Lagos (Segun et al., 2024).

2. Rationale of The Study :- An individual's parenting style has far-reaching effects on their offspring's character and conduct as well as the family unit. Therefore, it's crucial for everyone, parents included, to have a foundational understanding of child development, the many parenting styles, how they work, and the impact they have on kids. Individuals may cultivate good connections and establish nurturing situations for children to flourish by mastering the basics of child-rearing (Teuber, Z., Tang, X., Sielemann, L., Otterpohl, N., & Wild, E., 2022). Additionally, parents and their children benefit from a heightened understanding of various parenting styles since it empowers them to make well-informed decisions on childrearing. When parents are aware of the pros and cons of different parenting styles—authoritarian, permissive, and neglectful—they are better able to make decisions that are best for their children. In the end, a considerate parenting style can help bring up strong, self-assured people who are ready to face life's obstacles head-on.

4.0 Research Problem :- The present study aimed at the relationship between different parenting styles with students' aggression and self-esteem.

4.1 Objectives :-

1. To study the authoritarian parenting styles on students' aggression and self-esteem.
2. To study the authoritative parenting styles on students' aggression and self-esteem.
3. To study the permissive parenting styles on students' aggression and self-esteem.

4.2 Hypotheses :-

1. There will be no relationship between authoritative parenting styles, self-esteem, and aggression.
2. There will be no relationship between authoritarian parenting styles, self-esteem, and aggression.
3. There will be no relationship between permissive parenting styles, self-esteem, and aggression

4.3 Sampling technique :-

The researcher in this study relied on a non-probability convenience sample, which involves picking participants at random depending on how convenient it is for them to fill out the survey.

4.4 Sample Size :- The researcher took a Non-Probability Convenience sample of 100 students from the Khordha, Odisha area. Only male and female students were considered for the assessment. Students (aged 15–17) made up the majority of the study's subjects.

4.5 Tools :- The research made use of three (03) already developed questionnaires, including;

- A. The Parental Authority Questionnaire (PAQ) by John R. Buri (1989);
- B. The Rosenberg Self-esteem Scale (RSE) by Morris Rosenberg (1965);
- C. The Buss–Perry Aggression Questionnaire by Buss & Perry (1992);

4.6 Statistical Techniques :- The study's hypotheses were calculated using SPSS-V27. The descriptive statistics, Mean and SD, the person's product-moment correlation was employed and the t-test was computed for the investigation of mean differences.

5. a) Results :-

5.1 Demographic Results of the study :-

**Table 5.1
Demographic Results**

SL.NO	Demographic Variables	Frequency(N)	Per cent
1	Age		
	15-16	35	35%
	16-17	65	65%
2	Educational Qualification		
	10 th	45	45%
	11 th - 12 th	55	55%
3	Type of Family		
	Joint family	65	65%
	Nuclear family	35	35%
4	Total Number of Family Members		
	3- 5 members	47	47%
	6 and above members	53	53%

Hypothesis 1:

Table 5.2

Mean, SD, and t-value for authoritative parenting styles, self-esteem, and aggression.

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t value	p
Authoritative Parenting	Male	50	27.720	5.514	-.464	Insig .644> 0.05
	Female	50	28.220	5.253		

Self Esteem	Male	50	14.740	3.231		
					1.542	Insig .126> 0.05
	Female	50	13.720	3.380		
Aggression	Male	50	72.560	6.972	-4.130	
						Sig* .000< 0.05
	Female	50	78.320	6.973		

Note. **p < .01, *p < .05

The above T.5.2, The result indicates that the t value is -.464, p = .644, which is found to be Insignificant at both levels (0.05 and 0.01) in Authoritative Parenting, the t value is 1.542, p = .126, which is found to be Insignificant at both levels (0.05 and 0.01) in Self Esteem. Also, the result shows that the t value is -4.130, p = .000, which shows a significant result at a 0.05 level in aggression.

Table 5.3
Correlation between authoritative parenting styles, self-esteem, and aggression.

Variables	N	R	p
Authoritative Parenting vs Self Esteem	100	.048	Insig
Authoritative Parenting vs Aggression	100	.210	Sig*

“*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).”

From T.5.3, Study resulted a positive correlation among Authoritative and Aggression Parenting styles, it implies a positive relationship among Authoritative Parenting and Aggression (r= .210, p=0.000 < 0.05). Still, there is no correlation between Authoritative Parenting with Self self-esteem (r= .048, p= .632 > 0.05).

Hypothesis 2:

Table 5.4
Mean, SD, and t- value for authoritarian parenting styles, self-esteem, and aggression.

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t value	p
Authoritarian Parenting	Male	50	25.740	3.778		
					-.290	Insig .772>0.05
	Female	50	25.980	4.456		
Self Esteem	Male	50	14.740	3.231		
					1.542	Insig .126>0.05
	Female	50	13.720	3.380		
Aggression	Male	50	72.560	6.972	-4.130	
						Sig* .000<0.05
	Female	50	78.320	6.973		

“Note. **p < .01, *p < .05”

From T.5.4, shows the difference between Male and Female authoritarian parenting styles, self-esteem, and aggression. The result indicates that the t value is -.290, p = .772, which is found to be Insignificant at both levels (0.05 and 0.01) in Authoritative Parenting, the t value is 1.542, p = .126, which is found to be Insignificant at both levels (0.05 and 0.01) in Self Esteem. Also, the result shows that the t value is -4.130, p = .000, which is significant at a 0.05 level in aggression.

Table 5.5
Correlation between authoritative parenting styles, self-esteem, and aggression.

Variables	N	R	p
Authoritarian Parenting vs Self Esteem	100	.135	Insig
Authoritarian Parenting vs Aggression	100	.254	Sig*

***Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).**

From T.5.5 above, since there shows a positive correlation among Authoritarian Parenting and Aggression, it implies a positive relationship between Authoritarian Parenting and Aggression ($r = .254$, $p = 0.000 < 0.05$). Still, there is no correlation among Authoritarian Parenting and self-esteem ($r = .135$, $p = .632 > 0.05$).

Hypothesis 3:

Table 5.6
Mean, SD, and t- value for permissive parenting styles, self-esteem, and aggression.

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t value	p
Permissive Parenting	Male	50	23.100	3.512	-2.165	Sig* .033 > 0.05
	Female	50	24.640	3.601		
Self Esteem	Male	50	14.740	3.231	1.542	Insig .126 > 0.05
	Female	50	13.720	3.380		
Aggression	Male	50	72.560	6.972	-4.130	Sig* .000 < 0.05
	Female	50	78.320	6.973		

"Note. **p < .01, *p < .05"

The above Table 5.6 shows the difference between Male and Female permissive parenting styles, self-esteem, and aggression. The result indicates that the t value is -2.165, $p = .033$, which is found to be significant at 0.05 levels in permissive Parenting, the t value is 1.542, $p = .126$, which is found to be Insignificant at both levels (0.05 and 0.01) in Self Esteem. Also, the result shows that the t value is -4.130, $p = .000$, which is significant at a 0.05 level in aggression

Table 5.7
Correlation among permissive parenting styles, self-esteem, and aggression.

Variables	N	R	P
Permissive Parenting vs Self Esteem	100	.015	Insig
Permissive Parenting vs Aggression	100	.156	Insig

****Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)."**

From T. 5.7 above, since there is no correlation among Permissive Parenting Styles and Aggression, it implies no relationship among Permissive Parenting Styles and Aggression ($r = .156$, $p = 0.120 < 0.05$). Also, there is no correlation

between permissive Parenting with Self Esteem ($r = .015$, $p = .882 > 0.05$).

Discussion :- Table 5.1 provides firstly, most of the participants (65%) fall in age range of 16-17

years, with the remaining 35% aged between 15-16 years. This distribution indicates that the study primarily focuses on adolescents or young individuals. **Secondly**, the data shows that 55% of the respondents are 10th, while the remaining 45% are 12th students. **Thirdly**, the respondents' type of family is divided into joint families (65%) and nuclear families (35%). Lastly, the variable related to the total number of family members reveals that 53% of the respondents come from families with six or more members, while 45% belong to families with 3-5 members.

Tables 5.2 And 5.3 :-

Table 5.2 provides that both genders experience similar levels of authoritative Parenting and the lack of significant difference implies that gender does not play a significant role in the perception of authoritative parenting styles.

When examining self-esteem, shows that both genders have similar levels of self-esteem and there is a lack of significant difference suggests that gender does not have a substantial impact on self-esteem in this context.

As, Though, it's significant to message that individual differences and background factors can inspiration aggression levels, and these results should be interpreted with caution.

Moving to T.5.3, the authoritative Parenting is positively correlated with aggression but there is no significant correlation between authoritative Parenting and self-esteem. This suggests that authoritative parenting styles do not have a direct impact on self-esteem within the studied population.

Tables 5.4 And 5.5 :-

Table 5.4 shows there is presented no significant difference among males and females in terms of experiencing authoritarian Parenting.

When examining self-esteem, shows that there is presented no significant difference among males and females in terms of self-esteem.

But there is a significant difference presented in Aggression among males and females. The negative t-value proposes that, on typical, males tend to exhibit high level of

aggression related to females.

Moving to Table 5.5, reveals a positive correlation among authoritarian Parenting and aggression that indicates that high level of Authoritarian Parenting Styles is associated with higher levels of aggression within the studied population also the authoritarian parenting styles do not have a direct impact on self-esteem.

Tables 5.6 And 5.7 :-

Table 5.6 suggests that there are gender differences in the experience of permissive Parenting. The negative t-value indicates that, on average, females may perceive higher levels of permissive Parenting compared to males.

Regarding self-esteem, indicates no significant difference but in aggression, a significant difference among males and females. The negative t-value suggests that, on average, males tend to exhibit higher levels of aggression compared to females.

Table 5.7, no significant correlation between permissive Parenting and aggression, also with the permissive Parenting and self-esteem. This suggests that permissive parenting styles do not have a direct impact on self-esteem.

Conclusion :- The findings revealed that there is a substantial association between authoritative parenting styles and aggression, suggesting that higher degrees of authoritative Parenting may be related to increased violence. However, there is no substantial association between authoritarian parenting approaches and self-esteem. Also, there is a substantial association between authoritarian parenting styles and violence, suggesting that higher degrees of authoritarian Parenting may relate to increased aggression. Still, self-esteem and authoritarian parenting approaches don't go hand in hand. In this group of people, we found no evidence of a correlation between more lenient parenting techniques and lower levels of aggression or self-esteem. However, it's vital to highlight a considerable variance in the impression of permissive parenting approaches dependent on gender. These findings demonstrate that the connection between

parenting styles, aggression, and self-esteem is complex and that additional variables may have a role in these outcomes.

Limitations of the Study :-

- Respondents were only adolescents belonging to the age group of 15 to 17 years.
- Other demographic factors (area, age, strata group etc) were not studied.
- Only three (03) variables were studied.
- The geographical location only was one (Khordha) area.
- Only a quantitative study was done.

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